

Stimulus Responsive Polymer and Multifunctional Composites: Challenges and Prospects

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Stimulus Responsive Polymer and Composites are materials that have one or more properties can be significantly changed in a controlled fashion by external stimuli. Recently, a number of types of Stimulus Responsive Polymer and composites have been extensively developed on both materials innovation and applications exploration. This presentation mainly focuses on recent progresses of Shape Memory Polymer (SMP), and SMP based multifunctional composites, as well as their applications in aerospace, astronautics and biomedical engineering, etc..